

DCC2GO

Basic Knowledge on DCCs

Information for management at NMI and DIs

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Content and goal

- These slides are intended as common introduction to the Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) for management.
- The purpose is to support the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community by providing knowledge on aspects concerning management
- The slides are part of a knowledge compendium also containing a common introduction to DCCs and more specific information for technical staff and stakeholders of NMIs and DIs

Digital Transformation & DCC

“Digital transformation can refer to anything from IT modernization (for example, cloud computing), to digital optimization, to the invention of new digital business models. The term is widely used in public-sector organizations to refer to modest initiatives such as putting services online or legacy modernization. Thus, the term is more like “digitization” than “digital business transformation.” (Gartner IT glossary)

An implementation and usage of DCCs is one piece of puzzle for a wider digital upgrade of an organization, its processes and services.

Investments in introducing for example digital signatures will not only be useful for the DCCs but for many other services of an organization that need to be made digital too.

A wider implementation of DCCs is accompanied by needs for conducting change and thus, will require an involvement of management.

Introducing DCC

Legal and regulatory requirements

- The existing legal and regulatory requirements for calibration certificates also apply to DCCs.
 - Provided a DCC is fully replacing the non-digital calibration certificate.

DCCs can fulfil the existing requirements!

An easy introduction of DCCs could be based on having a conventional analogue certificate, that is already fulfilling all legal and regulatory requirements, accompanied by a DCC.

Introducing DCC

Legal and regulatory requirements

- **Example signature for DCCs:**

- eIDAS regulation defining legally valid methods for signing digital documents in EU
- Company policies may need to be updated to allow digital signatures (e.g., PTB had to update some policies).

- **Example secure storage of DCCs:**

- 5, 10 or more years needed depending on application
- Implementation of reliable longer term storage, e.g., suitable e-file systems
- Using data formats readable by humans and software for many years to the future (e.g., XML, JSON)

The ability to digitally sign and reliably store is of general interest for a digital transformation.

Phases of implementing DCC

Guidance on necessary resources to start with DCCs

EARLY STAGE

Developing creation/use of DCC for one type of measuring equipment
Effort by existing staff

- Identify needs**
- Training
 - Software
 - Hardware
 - Budget

MEDIUM TERM

Establishing DCC in Organization

- Several labs introducing DCCs
- Hardware & software for DCC creation, use, digital signatures, storage
- Maintenance of tools
- Training staff, new staff
- Coordination stakeholders

LONGER TERM

DCCs integrated in automated workflows in areas where appropriate

- Setting up intelligent (smart) facilities (reducing costs)
- Infrastructure for data exchange across automated processes and devices
- Tools for automation, monitoring and controlling workflows

Status of standardization of DCCs

Why is standardization needed for DCCs?

- Non-standardised data exchange formats are not sustainable as they require high costs for maintenance on the side of users and creators of calibration data and software.

What needs to be standardized?

- **Common formats for providing calibration data in digital and machine-readable form**
 - Common provision of content of first page (administrative data)
 - Unambiguous and clear representation of measurement data, methods, equipment, terminology, etc.
- **Measurand-specific representation of the calibration data**
 - It needs to be made very clear which information must be provided for each measurand
 - Standardization starts with a refinement of the existing analogue standards

Status of standardization of DCCs

Current Status of standardization for DCCs?

- Today, harmonization of DCC formats are driven by NMIs and industry. Several organizations have created committees to assess and progress the development and implementation of DCCs. Here are a few notable initiatives:
 - [EURAMET TC-IM project 1448](#) aims to foster the development of harmonised digital calibration certificates (DCC) at national metrology institutes and calibration laboratories with involvement of EURAMET's TCs.
 - [SIM MWG-14 on digital transformation for metrology](#) has established a task force for an exchange of information on DCC implementation across SIM's NMIs.
 - [PTB coordinating the advancement of the XML DCC format](#) and its standardization in a wider network of NMIs, DIs, and industry groups (DCC version 3 is long-term supported and used in first commercial products).
 - **DKD** (German Calibration Service) committees started to harmonize representation of data in DCCs for users from industry. (DOI 10.7795/550.20220419B)

Credits

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Supporting the implementation of Digital Calibration Certificates in the European metrology community

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